

Research Article

**Seroprevalence and molecular detection of Chikungunya virus
in serum of outpatients in selected area of
Telangana state of India**

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Abstract:

CHIKV (Chikungunya virus) has already been discovered in over 110 countries in Asia, Africa, Europe, and the Americas. Transmission has been interrupted on islands where a significant part of the population gets sick and then develops immune; yet, transmission routinely continues in countries where large segments of the population have not yet been afflicted.

Of the 29 samples, 20 were positive for antibodies against CHIKV, the 09 samples were negative. The positivity averages of IgM and IgG detected against CHIKV were 45% (27 ±29.61 (±109.67%))and 55%(33 ±36.19 (±109.67%)) respectively. Of the total number of patients involved in this study, 12 (60%) were women and 08 (40%) were men with the mean age of 27.50 years.

myalgia, Joint pain and Abdominal pain were the symptoms most reported by participants of this study. Fever, headaches, and myalgia were observed in all patients.

Public health initiatives, research advancements, and community engagement are crucial in combating Chikungunya and mitigating its negative effects on the population's quality of life.

Keywords: Serology, chikungunya, CHIKV, Elisa, Aedes aegypti

Introduction

Chikungunya is a viral disease transmitted by mosquitoes and caused by the Chikungunya virus (CHIKV), an RNA virus in the alphavirus genus of the family *Togaviridae*. Chikungunya is named after a Kimakonde phrase that means "to become contorted". CHIKV was initially discovered in the United Republic of Tanzania in 1952, and thereafter spread to other African and Asian nations [1]. Urban outbreaks were first recorded in Thailand in 1967 and in India in the 1970s [2]. Since 2004, CHIKV outbreaks have become more frequent and broad, thanks in part to viral modifications that make the virus easier to transmit by *Aedes albopictus* mosquitos. CHIKV has already been found in more than 110 countries across Asia, Africa, Europe, and the Americas. Transmission has been halted on islands where a major proportion of the population is sick and subsequently becomes immune; yet, transmission frequently continues in nations where huge portions of the population have not yet been affected. All regions with established populations of *Aedes aegypti* or *Aedes albopictus* mosquitoes have now experienced local mosquito-borne transmission. [3]

However, this polyarthralgia is recurrent in 30–40% of infected individuals and may persist for years [4]. The joint pain caused by CHIKV infection may be debilitating, which can limit even the simplest daily activities.

CHIKV – CHIKV is a member of the *Togaviridae* family, genus *Alphavirus*, and belongs to the Semliki Forest antigenic complex. Among the members of this antigenic complex are Mayaro, O’Nyong-nyong and Ross River viruses, all of which are capable of causing disease in humans [5].

Chikungunya is a positive-sense single-stranded RNA virus that is about 12 kb in size. The genome has two open reading frames. the 5’ORF, translated from genomic RNA, encodes the nsP1, nsP2, nsP3, and nsP4 non-structural proteins, and the 3’ORF, translated from subgenomic RNA, encodes a polyprotein that is processed into the structural proteins

[capsid (C), envelope (E1 and E2), and two peptides (E3 and 6K)] [4].

The viral particle is spherical, about 70 nm in diameter, made up of 240 copies of the capsid protein, and is enveloped by a lipid bilayer. Inserted in the envelope are 80 trimer-shaped spikes formed by E1 and E2 glycoproteins [6]. The transmission of arboviruses through patients' blood during the viraemic period may provide a significant challenge for blood donation in endemic locations. During the pandemic in La Reunion, the French blood service (*Etablissement Français du Sang*) suspended blood donations on the island. At the time, an estimated 47 of the 37,750 blood bags donated during the epidemic may have been contaminated if the donations had not been interrupted [7]. In a study that analysed the presence of viral RNA and specific IgG antibodies for CHIKV in samples collected before, during, and after the epidemics that occurred in Puerto Rico in 2014, 2.1% of the donations were positive for CHIKV RNA. Epidemiologic studies in this population showed that approximately 25% of blood donors were infected by CHIKV and seroconverted during the epidemics [8].

In India a major epidemic of Chikungunya fever was reported during the last millennium viz.; 1963 (Kolkata), 1965 (Pondicherry and Chennai in Tamil Nadu, Rajahmundry, Visakhapatnam, and Kakinada in Andhra Pradesh; Sagar in Madhya Pradesh; and Nagpur in Maharashtra) and 1973, (Barsi in Maharashtra). Thereafter, sporadic cases also continued to be recorded especially in Maharashtra state during 1983 and 2000.

Bilateral polyarthralgia is noted as a typical symptom affecting mainly the small joints such as ankles, wrist and phalanges and few large joints such as knees and elbows [9]. In about half of the cases, acute phase is also characterized by cutaneous lesions like maculopapular rashes, edematous or itchy skin affecting mainly the face and trunk [10]. Symptoms such as diarrhoea, abdominal pain, nausea, and vomiting are seen in 15–47% of individuals [6]. Other symptoms are asthenia,

erythema, persistent conjunctivitis, conjunctival effusion, and cervical lymphadenopathy. Moderate thrombocytopenia, leukopenia and lymphopenia are also common [1,12,13]. Severe symptoms like bleeding due to thrombocytopenia, bulbous skin lesions, hepatitis, meningoencephalitis, meningitis have been reported in a few patients[14-17]. Ocular complications like retinitis or uveitis, myocarditis, nephritis, cranial nerve palsies and Guillain-Barre Syndrome have been observed for the first time during the 2006 Indian Ocean outbreak [18-19]. Renal and neurological complications are also associated with severe chikungunya infection [15,20]. In few cases a very high viral load leads to persistence of the virus in minor joints during acute stage[11].

Epidemiology and Route of transmission

Source of infection

Patients and hidden sick persons are the primary sources of infection in urban epidemic source areas, with transmission primarily occurring through human-mosquito-human contact. In the early stages of the disease, 2-5 days can produce a high titer of viremia, which is extremely contagious. In the jungle epidemic foci, sick monkeys, orangutans, baboons and other primates, and wild animals are the main sources of infection of the disease, and the mode of transmission is mostly primate-mosquito-primate. [21].

Aedes aegypti is a domestic mosquito species found in tropical and subtropical cities and suburbs. It primarily breeds from water in small containers in residential areas. *Aedes africanus* is an African wild mosquito species that is hooked to primate blood and distributes viruses in wild animals, playing an important role in virus circulation in jungle-type foci.[22-23].

CHIKV presents similar signs and symptoms to other diseases such as Dengue, Malaria, Leptospirosis and Brucellosis [24]. *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* are the main vectors of CHIKV transmission to humans

[25]). CHIKV is transmitted through urban and sylvatic cycles. The urban cycle is the transmission of CHIKV from human to mosquito to human, while sylvatic transmission refers to the transmission of CHIKV from animal to mosquito to human [26].

After the emergence of CHIKV in the Indian Ocean islands in 2005, CHIKV re-emerged in India after 32 years [27], affecting Hyderabad and Ananthapur district of Andhra Pradesh in South India and eventually affected 1.4 million people in 13 states [28] with huge economic and productivity loss of 391 million rupees [29]. Ahmedabad city of Gujarat and Kerala state were the worst affected places [30]. The 2005–2006 outbreak in India was caused by the ECSA genotype [31-32]. The E1-A226V mutation of the virus and their adaptation to the *A. albopictus* resulted in increased susceptibility among pediatric population, neurological complications, as well as mortality associated with this outbreak [32]. However recently, some cases of CHIKV meningoencephalitis and myelopathy were reported from the Reunion Islands [33,34].

Monitoring the clinical features of CHIKV infection is an important component of assessing the disease process in humans so as to determine which organ system including the nervous system is affected. Laboratory tests are necessary to confirm the diagnosis of CHIKV. The immunoglobulin M (IgM) capture ELISA method, which provides evidence of CHIKV infection, is widely used to lend support to clinical findings in the assessment of patients with suspected CHIKV [35].

Ethics statement and inclusion criteria

This research involved people that were clinically diagnosed with some symptoms compatible with infection by arbovirus as fever, exanthema, headaches, myalgia, arthralgia and pruritus pain. No age or gender restrictions were applied. The study excluded people who were extremely unwell, such as those in a coma, or who needed to be hospitalized.

Methods statement

All methods described were performed in accordance with the relevant guidelines and regulations and were approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the M. Reddy Institute of Medical Sciences Hyderabad, Telangana, India

Materials and Methods

Study area

All the participants were recruited from Department of community medicine, M, Reddy Institute of Medical Sciences Hyderabad, India. Duration of the study Jan, 2023 to June, 2023. This study was carried out to determine the seroprevalence of CHIKV through detection of antibodies against CHIKV by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) among outpatients seeking healthcare in Hyderabad City, Telangana, India. Molecular assays were performed as the confirmatory test to detect CHIKV RNA.

Data collection:

The study collected plasma samples from patients who visited health facilities with symptoms consistent with arbovirus infection, including chills, headache, joint pains, dizziness, nausea, arthralgia, and rash. No age or gender restrictions were applied. The study excluded people who were extremely unwell, such as those in a coma, or who needed to be hospitalized. Clinicians used a standardized questionnaire to collect demographic information from patients, including age, gender, and clinical symptoms.

Method:

This study were conducted at M. Reddy Institute of Medical Sciences Hyderabad. The prevalence of IgM/IgG antibodies and of infections confirmed by RT-qPCR were presented with 90% confidence interval. Outpatients were assessed by a certified clinician at the health facility and enrolled as participants based on the inclusion criteria.

Serological analysis

The Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) was used to determine IgM and IgG levels in all plasma samples. Serum samples were analyzed for anti-CHIKV IgM antibodies using Abcam's ELISA Kit (Cambridge, UK) as per manufacturer's instructions. The assay's diagnostic specificity and sensitivity exceeded 90%. Measure the absorbance of all wells at 450 nm and record the absorbance values for each standard and sample. Dual wavelength reading using 620 nm as reference wavelength is recommended. Samples are considered POSITIVE if the absorbance value is higher than 10% over the cut-off. Samples with an absorbance value of 10% above or below the cutoff should not be considered as clearly positive or negative → grey zone. It is recommended to repeat the test again 2 - 4 weeks later with a fresh sample. If results in the second test are again in the grey zone the sample has to be considered NEGATIVE. Samples are considered NEGATIVE if the absorbance value is lower than 10% below the cut-off. Cut-off: 10 NTU, Grey zone: 9-11 NTU, Negative: <9 NTU, Positive: >11 NTU

Molecular analysis

All samples analyzed in the serology were subjected to analysis by RT-qPCR. The viral RNA was extracted using the QIAamp Viral RNA Mini kit (Qiagen) following the manufacturer's instructions. real time RT-PCR assays (Bio-Rad) were performed. This Kit contains primers, probes and controls. The thermal profile consisted of a reverse transcription step, this step runs at 50°C for 30 min. For to activate the enzyme at 95 °C for 5 min and 45 cycles of 95 °C for 15 s and 60 °C for 1 min for hybridization and extension. All of the techniques in this assay followed the manufacturer's instructions.

Statistical analysis

For Demographic analysis used Microsoft Office-Excel and The statistical analyzes were performed using SPSS® Statistics version 20.0.

Results

Of the 29 samples, 20 were positive for antibodies against CHIKV, the 09 samples were negative. The positivity averages of IgM and IgG detected against CHIKV were 45%

(27 ±29.61 (±109.67%)) and 55% (33 ±36.19 (±109.67%)) respectively. Of the total number of patients involved in this study, 12 (60%) were women and 08 (40%) were men with the mean age of 27.50 years.

Arbovirus	Antibodies	Serology	N=20	%(CI%)
CHIKV	IgM	+ve	9	45
	IgG	+ve	11	55

IgM Immunoglobulin M, IgG Immunoglobulin G, N Number of individuals; % Prevalence, CI Confidence Interval

Table 1: Detection of antibodies against CHIKV in the plasma samples of the patients

The patients have IgM/IgG antibodies against the arbovirus CHIKV. All nine positive IgM tests for CHIKV, as well as eleven positive IgG samples, were validated.

Clinical Features	Number of anti-CHIKV positive n=20	%
Fever	20	100
Headaches	20	100
Nausea	9	45
Joint pain	11	55
myalgia	20	100
pruritus	7	35
Abdominal pain	13	65

Our results are consistent with a study in Brazil where a seroprevalence of 18.3% of anti-CHIKV IgM antibodies was reported among rural community households with no acute clinical manifestations of CHIKF [40].

By detecting anti-CHIKV IgM specific antibodies, the results suggest a possibility of acute infections. Detection of anti-CHIKV IgM antibodies indicates that CHIKV is prevalent and contributes to the burden on Telangana state.

We note that fever, Nausea, headaches, myalgia, Joint pain and Abdominal pain were the symptoms most reported by participants of

this study. Fever, headaches, and myalgia were observed in all patients.

Discussion:

The results indicate a high seroprevalence of 68.96% of CHIKF as detected by presence of anti-CHIKV IgM antibodies in patients' sera. This is despite not testing for anti-CHIKV IgG antibodies and therefore the overall seroprevalence of CHIKF in this population may be underestimated. IgG antibodies against CHIKV indicate if a population is naïve or the patients have a pre-exposure to the pathogen before [35]. The first report on CHIKV infection with neurological complication was

reported in the 1960 s. There were some reports which suggest that this infection was found to be associated with meningoencephalitis, myelitis, and choroiditis [36,37].

In the present study, we analyzed the serological and molecular epidemiology of CHIKV in city of Hyderabad in Telangana state. We discovered that these viruses spread concurrently inside the state, primarily in the metropolitan region of hyderabad, which has raised the necessity for serological testing. However, these assays have limitations owing to cross reactivity during arbovirus diagnosis. The diagnostic sensitivity of CHIKV antigen detection utilizing an ELISA-based technique is better than that of traditional IgM and IgG tests, and it aids in the identification of antigen throughout the illness, including the early stages. It should also be noted that serological diagnostic tests are challenged by the patient-specific infection histories and it is important to be conscious of the potential regional limitations of serological tests [39]. This suggests that creating a bioinformatic infrastructure for an infectious pathogen might be extremely beneficial in tracking and establishing a treatment and preventive plan to limit disease transmission. In the hunt for CHIKV vaccinations, mRNA vaccine technology provides fresh hope.

Chikungunya, caused by the Chikungunya virus (CHIKV), has been a significant public health concern in India. The disease is characterized by acute and self-limiting symptoms such as high fever, joint pain, headache, muscle pain, rash, and fatigue. While CHIKV infection has low mortality rates, it can cause a painful and debilitating illness, impacting the quality of life for affected individuals.

In India, Chikungunya outbreaks have been reported in various states and union territories, 24 Indian states and six union territories are considered endemic for CHIKV. The virus is primarily transmitted to humans through the bite of infected *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* mosquitoes, which are also

responsible for transmitting other mosquito-borne diseases like dengue and Zika.

The painful course of illness associated with Chikungunya, along with its long-term sequelae, poses significant challenges to the affected population. While the acute symptoms generally resolve within a few weeks, some individuals may experience persistent joint pain, known as post-chikungunya chronic arthritis. This long-term complication can last for months or even years, affecting mobility and overall quality of life. Efforts to control and prevent Chikungunya in India have focused on mosquito control measures, including the elimination of breeding sites and public awareness campaigns to promote personal protection against mosquito bites. Additionally, healthcare providers play a crucial role in early detection, diagnosis, and management of Chikungunya cases to alleviate symptoms and provide appropriate care. It's important for individuals residing in or traveling to Chikungunya-endemic areas to take precautions to prevent mosquito bites, such as using insect repellents, wearing protective clothing, and eliminating standing water where mosquitoes can breed.

Public health initiatives, research advancements, and community engagement are crucial in combating Chikungunya and mitigating its negative effects on the population's quality of life.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Ethical approval was obtained from M. Reddy Institute of Medical Sciences Hyderabad, India. Oral and written consent was obtained from the community members and health workers, respectively, after explaining the objective of the study.

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Availability of data and materials

The dataset analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on a reasonable request.

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